

Power of 2 Decomposition of a Complete Tripartite Graph $K_{2,4,M}$ and a Special Butterfly Graph

V. G. Smilin Shali, S. Asha

Abstract: Let G be a finite, connected simple graph with p vertices and q edges. If G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n are connected edge-disjoint subgraphs of G with $E(G) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \dots \cup E(G_n)$, then $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is said to be a decomposition of G . A graph G is said to have Power of 2 Decomposition if G can be decomposed into edge-disjoint subgraphs $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ such that each G_i is connected and $|E(G_i)| = 2^i$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Clearly, $q = 2[2^n - 1]$. In this paper, we investigate the necessary and sufficient condition for a complete tripartite graph $K_{2,4,m}$ and a Special Butterfly graph $BF\left[\frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3}\right]$ to accept Power of 2

Decomposition.

Keywords : Decomposition of Graph, Power of 2 Decomposition, Complete tripartite graph, Special Butterfly graph.

I. INTRODUCTION

Let G be a simple, connected graph with p vertices and q edges. If G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n are connected edge-disjoint subgraphs of G with $E(G) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \dots \cup E(G_n)$, then $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is said to be a Decomposition of G . Different type of decomposition of G have been studied in the literature by imposing suitable conditions on the subgraphs G_i . In this paper, we investigate the necessary and sufficient condition for a Complete tripartite graph $K_{2,4,m}$ and a Special Butterfly graph to accept a new type of decomposition called Power of 2 Decomposition. Terms not defined here are used in the sense of Harary [2].

Definition 1.1. Let G be a simple graph of order p and size q . If G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n are edge-disjoint subgraphs of G such that $E(G) = E(G_1) \cup E(G_2) \cup \dots \cup E(G_n)$, then $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ is said to be a Decomposition of G .

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II. POWER OF 2 DECOMPOSITION OF GRAPHS

Definition 2.1. A graph G is said to have Power of 2 Decomposition [Po2D], if G can be decomposed into n subgraphs $\{G_1, G_2, \dots, G_n\}$ such that each G_i is connected and $|E(G_i)| = 2^i$, for $1 \leq i \leq n$. Clearly $q = 2[2^n - 1]$ is the sum of $2, 2^2, 2^3, \dots, 2^n$. Thus, we denote the Power of 2 Decomposition as $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$. Example 2.2. Consider the graph.

$K_{1,2,4} [(4,3) - \text{Fan graph}]$

Complete tripartite graph $K_{1,2,4}$ admits Power of 2 Decomposition $\{G_2, G_4, G_8\}$ as follows.

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Illustration 3.3. As an illustration, let us decompose the Complete tripartite graph $K_{2,4,9}$. Let $G = K_{2,4,9}$. Here $m = 9$. Hence $2^n = 32$. Thus $n = 5$. Hence there will be 5 decompositions. The Power of 2 Decomposition of G is $\{G_2, G_4, G_8, G_{16}, G_{32}\}$ and is given as follows.

Theorem 2.3. A graph G admits Power of 2 Decomposition [Po2D] $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$ if and only if $q = 2[2^n - 1]$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

III. POWER OF 2 DECOMPOSITION OF $K_{2,4,m}$

Definition 3.1. A Complete tripartite graph is a tripartite graph whose vertices are decomposed into three disjoint sets such that no two vertices within the same set are adjacent but every pair of vertices in the three sets are adjacent. A Complete tripartite graph is denoted as $K_{a,b,c}$ where a, b and c are three disjoint sets of vertices of the graph.

Theorem 3.2. For an odd integer m , $K_{2,4,m}$ has a Power of 2 Decomposition $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$ [n -decompositions] if and only if there exists an integer n satisfying the following properties.

1. $n = 2r + 1, r \geq 1$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}$.
2. $2^n = 5 + 3m$

Proof. Let $G = K_{2,4,m}$. Assume that G has Power of 2 Decomposition $\{G_2, G_4, G_8, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$. By the definition,

$q = 2[2^n - 1]$, where n denotes the total number of decompositions. By the definition of G , $q = 8 + 6m$. Hence $2[2^n - 1] = 8 + 6m$. This implies $2^n = 5 + 3m$. Since 2^n is even, $5 + 3m$ is even. Hence m is odd.

Case 1. n is even.

Then $5 + 3m$ should be a power value of 4. This is not possible for any odd integer m . Hence n cannot be even.

Case 2. n is odd.

Clearly $5 + 3m$ should be written as a power value of 2, as $5 + 3m$ is even. Hence n is odd.

Thus $n = 2r + 1, r \geq 1$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}$.

Conversely, assume that $n = 2r + 1, r \geq 1$ and $r \in \mathbb{Z}$. Also, $2^n = 5 + 3m$. Hence m is odd. By the definition of G , $q = 8 + 6m$.

This implies $q = 8 + 6 \left[\frac{2^n - 5}{3} \right] = 8 + 2[2^n - 5] = 2[2^n - 1]$.

Since $q = 2[2^n - 1]$, G can be decomposed into $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$. Hence G admits Power of 2 Decomposition.

Table 3.4. List of first 10 $K_{2,4,m}$'s which accept Power of 2 Decomposition and their decompositions are given in the following table.

m	Power of 2 Decompositions
1	G_2, \dots, G_8
9	G_2, \dots, G_{32}
41	G_2, \dots, G_{128}
169	G_2, \dots, G_{512}
681	G_2, \dots, G_{2048}
2729	G_2, \dots, G_{8192}
10,921	G_2, \dots, G_{32768}
43,689	G_2, \dots, G_{131072}
174,761	G_2, \dots, G_{524288}
699,049	$G_2, \dots, G_{2097152}$

IV. POWER OF 2 DECOMPOSITION OF SPECIAL BUTTERFLY GRAPH

Definition [5] 4.1. Consider the cycle C_{2t+2} , $t \geq 4$. Let $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{2t+1}$ be the vertices of the cycle C_{2t+2} . Join a_0 and a_{2i-1} , $2 \leq i \leq t$. Attach two pendant edges at a_t and a_{t+2} . Let the vertices attached with those edges be a_{2t+2}, a_{2t+3} respectively. This is called the Special Butterfly Graph and it is denoted by BF_t . The graph BF_t has $2t + 4$ vertices and $3t + 3$ edges.

Theorem 4.2. A Special Butterfly Graph $BF_{\left\lceil \frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3} \right\rceil}$ admit

Power of 2 Decomposition $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$ if and only if $n = 2m, m \in \mathbb{N}$.

Proof. Assume that $G = BF_{\left\lceil \frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3} \right\rceil}$ admit Power of 2

Decomposition $\{G_2, G_4, \dots, G_{2^n}\}$. By the definition of G ,

$$q = 3 \left\lceil \frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3} \right\rceil + 3 = 2^{2m+1} - 2. \text{ Since } G \text{ admit Power of}$$

2 Decomposition, $q = 2[2^n - 1]$. Hence $2^{2m+1}-2 = 2[2^n-1]$. This implies $n = 2m$.

Conversely, assume that $n = 2m, m \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $G = BF_{\left\lceil \frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3} \right\rceil}$. Then $q(G) = 2^{2m+1} - 2$. This implies

$q = 2[2^n - 1]$. Decompose the edges of G as follows:

$$G_2 = a_{t+2} a_{t+3} \cup a_{t+3} a_{t+4},$$

$$G_4 = a_{2t+2} a_t \cup a_t a_{t+1} \cup a_{t+1} a_{t+2} \cup a_{t+2} a_{2t+3},$$

$$G_8, G_{32}, \dots, G_{2^{n-1}} = \cup a_0 a_{2i-1}, \quad 2 \leq i \leq t \quad \text{and}$$

$$G_{16}, G_{64}, \dots, G_{2^n} = a_0 a_{2t+1} \cup a_{i-1} a_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq t \text{ and}$$

$$t + 5 \leq i \leq 2t + 1$$

Thus G can be decomposed using Power of 2 Decomposition.

Illustration 4.3. As an illustration, let us decompose the Special Butterfly Graph BF_9 .

Let $G = BF_9$. Here $t = 9 = \frac{2^{4+1}-5}{3}$. Hence $2m = n = 4$.

There will be 4 decompositions $\{G_2, G_4, G_8, G_{16}\}$. The Power of 2 Decomposition of BF_9 is given below.

Table 4.4. List of first 10 Special Butterfly Graphs G_{16} $BF_{\left\lceil \frac{2^{2m+1}-5}{3} \right\rceil}$ which accept Power of 2 Decomposition and its decompositions are given in the following table.

m	Power of 2 Decompositions
1	G_2, G_4
2	G_2, G_4, G_8, G_{16}
3	G_2, \dots, G_{64}
4	G_2, \dots, G_{256}
5	G_2, \dots, G_{1024}

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6	G_2, \dots, G_{4096}
7	G_2, \dots, G_{16384}
8	G_2, \dots, G_{65536}
9	G_2, \dots, G_{262144}
10	$G_2, \dots, G_{1048576}$

V. CONCLUSION

Thus we had investigated the properties of two special graphs to accept a new type of graph decomposition called Power of 2 Decomposition. Also we can extend the study to various types of special graphs.

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